

CAP AND AGROFORESTRY

Enhancing agroforestry in the CAP

THE WHAT AND WHY

Agroforestry the way to increase sustainable land use systems in Europe

Agricultural lands in Europe are associated to intensive farming systems that reduce the delivery of ecosystem services (ES). Agroforestry (AF) should be strongly supported by the CAP as a sustainable land management option that provides market and non-market goods and services that address societal goals. Governments need to develop policies and actions that foster AF within an EU policy framework. However, AF is not extensively known by farmers in their broad FAO definition; the deliberate integration of woody vegetation (trees and/or shrubs) as an upper storey on land, with pasture (animals consumed) or an agricultural crop in the lower storey. Woody species can be evenly/unevenly distributed or be located on the border of plots, providing forestry/agricultural products or

other ES (i.e. provisioning, regulating or cultural). AF can take place at a range of scales (e.g. plot, farm and landscape). At farm and landscape scale it can be implemented in systems that are able to diversify production (e.g. food, forage, timber and fuelwood), provide ES (e.g. climate regulation and biodiversity enhancement), thus increasing both resilience and profitability. Mosquera-Losada et al. (2016) describes five main types of AF practices. Silvopasture and silvoarable are the main subjacent AF practices. In order to facilitate AF recognition and implementation, considering their important role in biodiversity, water issues and pollination, we have extended "riparian buffer strip" category to include any kind of hedgerows and windbreaks.

Sheep and cherry tree agroforestry system in Galicia (NW Spain).
Rodríguez-Rigueiro, FJ.

European Economic and Social Committee thematic session on the CAP.
European Economic and Social Committee.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Promoting agroforestry in Europe

- Agroforestry promotion should follow 15 key points highlighted in the AGFORWARD project.
- Agroforestry definition should be the one described by the FAO
- The CAP should identify, recognize and foster the use of five agroforestry practices across Europe: silvopasture; silvoarable; hedgerows, windbreaks and riparian buffer strips; forest farming and homegardens. An 'agroforestry option' would be self-declared by the farmer in the direct payments of the CAP and supported/evidenced by a management plan, and they should be fully eligible when agricultural land is involved.
- In the EU CAP context, it is useful to distinguish between "agroforestry practices on agricultural land" and "agroforestry practices on forest land"; this is also useful for considering

the circular and bioeconomy framework, carbon accounting and EU directives.

- There should be a single "agroforestry" measure, encompassing the five agroforestry types linked to agriculture, forestry and peri-urban lands, linked to result-based payments as it has substantial potential to contribute to European SDG targets.
- The EU should support co-operation measures which allow the benefits of agroforestry to be recognised within the value chain that can be achieved by facilitating co-operation among different actors along the value chain.
- Agroforestry needs to be supported through excellent EIP-Agri with extension services promotion, knowledge co-creation should be promoted under relevant Pillar II measures.

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Keywords: Pillar I, Pillar II Rural Development Programmes

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Agroforestry is a sustainable land use system that should be promoted by the CAP.
- Pillar I should support agroforestry on their 3 types of lands through the recognition of management plans at short and long term.
- Pillar II should support the establishment and maintenance of agroforestry in agricultural and forestry lands, and in the first case to ensure the land to remain eligible.
- Agroforestry transition should be promoted through the development of innovation and extension services.

Mushrooms production in forest boundaries.
López-Garre, Enrique

FURTHER INFORMATION

Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Santiago Freijanes, J.J., Pisanelli, A., Rois, M., Smith, J., den Herder, M., Moreno, G., Lamersdorf, N., Ferreiro Domínguez, N., Balaguer, F., Pantera, A., Papanastasis, V., Rigueiro-Rodríguez, A., Aldrey, J.A., Gonzalez-Hernández, P., Fernández-Lorenzo, J.L., Romero-Franco, R., Lampkin, N., Burgess, P.J. (2017). Deliverable 8.24: How can policy support the appropriate development and uptake of agroforestry in Europe? 7 September 2017. 21 pp. https://www.agforward.eu/index.php/es/how-can-policy-support-the-uptake-of-agroforestry-in-europe.html?file=files/agforward/documents/Deliverable%208_24%20How%20can%20policy%20support%20agroforestry%281%29.pdf

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

CAP recognition of agroforestry

CAP recognition of agroforestry will allow farming systems to move towards the needed transition from intensive farming systems towards more sustainable land use systems.

The recognition of agroforestry as such will help to simplify the CAP.

The adoption of agroforestry definition given by the FAO will allow to account in a better form for international bodies linked to the carbon accountability (IPCC)

Agroforestry can be implemented in any type of land and the advantages that agroforestry provides have to be recognized in all of them.

A clear support of agroforestry at the farm and landscape scales and cooperation measures among farmers should be considered to foster the benefits that at temporal and spatial scale agroforestry has.

The lack of knowledge about the implementation of agroforestry by farmers should be overcome through the enhancement of the innovation and extension services in Europe.

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